

EFFECT OF AUDIT QUALITY INDICATORS ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF QUOTED INSURANCE COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Underscoring the importance of scrutinizing the financial statements and accounts of companies cannot be overstated, as it instils confidence and enhances investor trust in the management's performance. Regular attention to assessing the factors influencing the quality of the audit process and their impact on achieving the corporate objective of maximizing shareholders' wealth is essential. Against this backdrop, this research investigates the influence of audit quality indicators on the financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria spanning the period from 2011 to 2022. The specific goals include examining the impact of audit fees, the size of audit firms, and the independence of audit committees on return on equity (ROE), a metric gauging financial performance. The study encompasses the entire population of Twenty-two insurance companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) Limited as of December 31, 2022. Employing an ex-post facto research design, the model estimation employs Random Effect Regression, as specified by both Lagrangian Multiplier and Hausman Specification tests. The findings reveal a noteworthy negative correlation between audit fees and financial performance, while audit firm size and audit committee independence show insignificant positive effects on the financial performance of the companies under scrutiny. Consequently, the study suggests that undue emphasis on the magnitude of fees paid should be avoided. Instead, more companies should consider engaging the services of prominent audit firms, particularly those classified as the big four (big 4). Furthermore, the appointment of additional independent directors to audit committees is recommended to enhance the financial performance of Nigerian insurance companies.

KEYWORDS: Audit Committee Independence, Audit Fee, Audit Firm Size. Audit Quality Indicator, Financial Performance and Return on Equity.

Introduction

Financial performance involves a comprehensive assessment of a company's overall status across various categories, including assets, liabilities, equity, expenses, revenue, and overall profitability. Business-related indices are utilized to evaluate financial performance, providing users of financial information with clear insights into a company's potential effectiveness. The survival of a firm relies on its ability to adeptly manage both financial and non-financial activities. Addressing financial performance and devising strategies for improvement are crucial considerations for corporate organizations, investors, and other stakeholders. According to Sayyar *et al.* (2015), enhancing a firm's performance can be achieved through the quality of

services provided by auditors, known as audit quality, as manifested in the fees charged for audit services. Shaibu and Abdullahi (2021) noted that the audit of the financial statements of firms is a form of external control where an independent auditor scrutinizes the activities of management to promote the quality of the information therein

As highlighted by Ahmeti *et al.* (2022), audit quality plays a vital role in enabling companies to achieve efficient and effective resource management, leading to rapid improvements in financial performance. Audit quality, in this context, focuses on offering independent assurance that an organization's risk management, governance, and internal control processes operate effectively and efficiently. The quality of an audit is gauged by various factors, including audit fees (Alrashidi *et al.*, 2021), the size of the audit firm, the auditor's independence, the duration of the auditor-client relationship, the financial expertise of audit committee members, and the size of the audit committee, among other considerations (Ehiedu & Toria, 2022). These factors, both individually and collectively, are interconnected with financial performance. The audit fee typically correlates with the auditor's skill, knowledge, and expertise, influencing the firm's performance (Hyarat *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, the size of the auditor or auditing firm plays a crucial role, as larger auditors possess more resources to conduct a comprehensive and unbiased audit, providing a more accurate assessment of the firm's true state (Ifurueze *et al.*, 2022). The independence of auditors is pivotal in determining the extent of disclosures in the audit report, with greater independence enabling auditors to express their opinions impartially and without any bias or influence (Eyenubo *et al.*, 2017).

An insurance company assumes the responsibility of managing insured risks and operates as a non-bank financial services institution offering a range of both financial and non-financial services. Within the realm of insurance, the provision of financial support aims to mitigate uncertainties in businesses by granting coverage against potential losses through indemnity from paid premiums. The role of insurance firms extends to facilitating the distribution of risk from the insured party to the insurer. The idea of insurance, as described by Weisbart (2018), is defined as a dynamic industry within the Nigerian economy, catering to particular requirements to stimulate economic activities.

The existing literature reveals a divergence of opinions regarding the impact of audit quality on the financial performance of corporate organizations. While certain scholars, such as Hyarat *et*

al. (2023) and Idogho and Daniel (2020), assert a significant influence of audit quality on financial performance, others like Monamesti and Agasha (2020) and Mustafa and Muhammad (2018) contend that the effect is inconsequential. This conflicting array of findings creates an avenue for further exploration, which this study aims to address. Notably, recent studies in both Nigeria and abroad exhibit a common shortcoming of lacking up-to-date information. For instance, studies by Hyarat *et al.* and Afifa and Saleh in 2023 covered the periods 2014-2018 and 2012-2017, respectively. Similarly, the latest Nigerian studies by Afolabi and Fawale (2022), Ehiedu and Toria (2022), Mbah *et al.* (2022), Orji and Nwaeze (2022), and Ozegbe and Jeroh (2022) spanned between 2003 and 2020, omitting data from 2021 and 2022, thereby diminishing the currency of these investigations.

The primary objective of this study is to assess the impact of audit quality indicators on the financial performance of quoted insurance companies in Nigeria spanning the years 2012 to 2022. The specific objectives include: i) analyzing the influence of audit fees on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria; ii) evaluating the impact of audit firm size on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria; and iii) determining the effect of audit committee independence on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. To achieve these specific objectives, two-tailed null hypotheses were formulated as follows: Ho1: Audit fee has no significant effect on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. Ho2: Audit firm size has no significant effect on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. Ho3: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Audit Quality Indicators Audit quality indicators can be characterized as the elements influencing the thoroughness of an audit in accurately portraying a business's financial position. The International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB; 2014) recognizes the absence of a universally accepted definition for audit quality. Afifa and Saleh (2023) assert that audit quality holds the potential to benefit multiple stakeholders by curbing managerial opportunism in earnings management, thereby ensuring the credibility of performance information. According to Ayora and Ogeto (2022), audit plays an essential role in overseeing management activities, specifically in scrutinizing the utilization of shareholders' funds over a

defined period. Megeid (2022) defines audit quality as comprising the attributes of the audit company, the audit team, corporate governance processes, and the methodologies employed in conducting audits, ultimately leading to satisfaction among various stakeholders. Ivungu et al. (2019) argue that gauging audit quality among stakeholders is primarily contingent on their specific information requirements. In the context of this study, audit quality is delineated as the reliability of audited financial statements, with representation through audit fees, audit firm size, and audit committee independence.

Audit Fees

Audit fees are the remuneration provided to professional auditors for the validation of financial statements in adherence to International Standards on Auditing (ISA) No. 15 (2011). Ogbonna *et al.* (2020) describe audit fees as encompassing all payments made by a client company to external auditors for both audit and non-audit services, including management advisory, consultancy, wages, benefits of office and field personnel, travel expenses, and other costs essential for the audit and associated support activities, along with a profit margin. Onaolapo *et al.* (2017) define audit fees as the amount an auditor charges for work done to express an opinion on the true and fair state of affairs or position of the client's business entity. According to Olutokunbo *et al.* (2020), an audit fee is the compensation paid by a client company to an auditing firm for the examination of its financial statements. Ugwu *et al.* (2020) observe that when a client incurs extraordinary audit costs due to a strong economic auditor-client relationship, it could potentially compromise the external auditors' ability to effectively oversee the company. In the context of this study, audit fees denote the charges imposed on a client company for the services rendered by an audit firm.

Audit Firm Size

The definition of an audit firm's size encompasses its overall net worth, including assets, number of employees, competence, and client base, all of which facilitate the auditing process. Typically, audit firms are categorized into big4 and non-big4, with Ifurueze *et al.* (2022) emphasizing that large, internationally affiliated firms execute audit engagements more expeditiously than their smaller counterparts. Eshleman and Guo (2014) assert that the size of an accounting firm, particularly whether it belongs to the Big4 or non-Big4 category, serves as a significant indicator of the audit's nature. The Big 4 audit firms—Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG),

PricewaterhouseCoopers (PWC), Ernst & Young (E&Y), and Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu (Deloitte) are specifically highlighted. To Ehiedu and Toria (2022), an audit is deemed high quality when conducted by Big4 firms due to their increased resources, extensive personnel training, and expertise. In the context of this study, the size of an audit firm pertains to whether it is part of the Big 4 audit firms or not.

Audit Committee Independence

Concerning Audit Committee Independence, it refers to the degree to which the committee operates without interference in fulfilling its oversight functions. This is often assessed by the percentage of independent non-executive directors who lack a stake in the company within the audit committee. The independence of an audit committee is realized when its members' monitoring mechanisms remain uncompromised (Al-Farooque *et al.*, 2019). An independent audit committee is characterized by members who can execute their monitoring role without interference from managers and auditors (Eyenubo *et al.*, 2017). Salehi *et al.* (2017) identify the independence of audit committee members as the most crucial factor influencing a firm's performance among various audit committee characteristics. Mugwe (2018) underscores the importance of an audit committee being independent of an organization's personnel and operational activities to maintain the credibility of auditors' opinions, conclusions, and recommendations. In the context of this study, audit committee independence is defined as the proportion of independent non-executive directors on the audit committee.

Financial Performance

Ivungu *et al.* (2019) defined financial performance as the evaluation of an entity's value, assessed through both accounting measures and market indicators of performance. They emphasized that the financial well-being of an entity is reflected in its ability to leverage assets for revenue generation from operations. Verma (2021) observed that financial performance involves estimating the monetary outcomes of a firm's activities and operations. Maka and Suresh (2018) argued that a company's financial performance demonstrates the effectiveness of management in utilizing resources to attain desired results and meet budgetary expectations, serving as a gauge of organizational activity efficiency and effectiveness.

Attah *et al.* (2021) highlighted that assessing profitability, a key indicator of financial performance, can be accomplished through metrics such as return on assets (ROA), return on

equity (ROE), profit after tax (PAT), and earnings per share (EPS). Specifically, return on equity (ROE) is crucial in measuring the returns generated with shareholders' equity. In the context of this study, return on equity (ROE) is adopted as the measure of financial performance, representing the effectiveness of utilizing shareholders' funds to generate profits.

Empirical Review

Hyarat *et al.* (2023) examined the direct correlation between audit quality (AQ) and the performance of non-financial companies in Jordan. The specific objectives included investigating the impact of audit fees on firms' return on assets (Tobin's Q) and assessing the moderating effect of ownership concentration. The study encompassed 92 public companies listed on the Stock Exchange of Amman (ASE) in the services and industry sectors, spanning the years 2014 to 2018. The data analysis employed partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The study's outcomes indicated a significant positive association between audit fees and firm performance, as well as a positive and significant effect of ownership concentration on firm performance. Additionally, the study revealed that ownership concentration, as a moderator, led to a statistically significant impact of audit quality on firm performance. The researchers recommended that future investigations explore alternative methodologies, such as interviews or self-administered surveys, to provide deeper insights into the role of different ownership types in enhancing audit quality. It is noteworthy that the study faced a limitation concerning the currency of data, with the latest dataset available being from 2018.

Afifa and Saleh investigated the impact of audit quality on the performance of companies in the Jordanian market. Their specific goals were to examine the influence of auditor tenure, auditor industry specialization, and audit firm size on metrics such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and earnings per share (EPS). Utilizing panel data spanning the years 2012-2017, the researchers found that auditor tenure had a significant negative effect on ROA. Auditor industry specialization showed no significant impact on ROE, while audit firm size demonstrated a notable effect on ROE. Moreover, audit firm size positively affected both ROE and EPS, whereas auditor tenure and auditor industry specialization had insignificant negative effects on both ROE and EPS. The study recommended that future research should focus on identifying factors influencing audit quality, particularly in emerging economies where there has been

limited exploration of the relationships between audit quality and other variables. Additionally, the use of 2017 data in a 2023 study raises concerns about the currency of the findings.

Orji and Nwaeze (2022) investigated the cause-and-effect relationship between audit fees paid by Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria and their financial performance. The primary objective was to assess the impact of audit fees on return on assets. The research utilized an *ex-post facto* research design, employing panel data extracted from the financial reports of ten banks in Nigeria spanning from 2014 to 2020. Firm size and leverage were introduced as moderating variables. The data were analyzed using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) Model in E-views version 10. The findings indicated a positive and significant correlation between audit fees and the financial performance of banks, while firm size and leverage exhibited a negative yet significant association with financial performance. The study's recommendations included the importance for bank management to ensure that audit fees charged by auditors contribute to enhanced audit quality, crucial for the confidence of financial users. Additionally, the study acknowledged the appropriateness of the Generalized Method of Moments regression method for panel data analysis, but it noted currency-related issues with the 2020 data being the most recent.

Mbah *et al.* (2022) delved into the influence of audit fees on the market performance of industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The specific objective was to scrutinize the connection between audit fees and the prices of shares. The research encompassed a sample of 18 publicly traded industrial goods firms in Nigeria, covering the period from 2011 to 2020. Employing an *ex-post facto* research design, the study subjected formulated hypotheses to preliminary data examinations, including descriptive statistics, Pearson Correlation analysis, and Variance Inflation Factor. The data underwent analysis using Panel regression analysis. The findings revealed a negative and statistically insignificant correlation between audit fees (AUDFE) and the market performance of industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The research suggested an enhanced regulatory focus on audit practices and fees in Nigeria. Despite the utilization of appropriate statistical tools, the study encountered certain challenges, particularly regarding currency issues, with 2020 being the most recent year of available data.

Ehiedu and Toria (2022) studied the examination of audit indicators and financial performance within the Nigerian manufacturing sector spanning the years 2003-2020 (18 years). The primary goals were to investigate the influence of auditor's independence, Audit Firm Size, Audit

Committee, and audit committee financial expertise on earnings per share (EPS). The study focused on three specific companies: Unilever Nigeria Plc., Beta Glass Plc., and Meyer Plc. Data for the analysis were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of these firms. The estimation method employed was Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), and various statistical tests, including normality, serial correlation, and heteroskedasticity, were conducted using the EVIEWS 9 statistical package. The findings revealed a significant impact of the audit committee and the audit committee's financial expertise on the earnings per share of Unilever Nigeria Plc. For Beta Glass Plc. and Meyer Plc., the study highlighted a significant influence of Audit Committee meetings, audit independence, and audit committee financial expertise on their respective earnings per share. Notably, the study refrained from offering specific recommendations. It is worth noting that the research chose to adopt OLS regression for panel data without pooling it, and the extended 18-year timeframe contributed to the robustness of the findings.

Amahalu and Obi (2020) investigated the impact of audit quality on the financial performance of quoted conglomerates in Nigeria spanning the years 2010 to 2019. The specific objectives included assessing the influence of audit committee size, audit committee independence, and audit committee financial expertise on return on assets. The researchers analyzed panel data extracted from the annual reports and accounts of six sampled quoted conglomerates over the 2010-2019 period, employing an ex-post facto research design. Inferential statistics, specifically the Pearson correlation coefficient and Panel Least Square (PLS) regression analysis, were utilized to test the study's hypotheses. The findings indicated that audit committee size, audit committee independence, and audit committee financial expertise each had a significant positive impact on return on assets at a 5% level of significance. The study's recommendations included advising conglomerates in Nigeria to adhere strictly to the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) provisions, ensuring a balanced representation of six members—three shareholders and three directors—for enhanced performance. The inclusion of 2019 data in the 2020 study and the application of PLS for panel data analysis were noted as contributing to the currency and appropriateness of the findings.

Theoretical Review

Theory of Inspired Trust and Value Creation

The Limperg Institute in the Netherlands introduced the Theory of Inspired Trust and Value Creation in 1985. According to this theory, auditors, acting as confidential agents, derive their societal role from the necessity of providing expert and independent examination and judgment supported by analyses. Consequently, accountants and auditors are tasked with recognizing the public's expectation of minimal audit failures and must accordingly plan and execute audits to minimize the risk of undetected material misstatements. The theory posits that individuals, assumed to be rational decision-makers, base their decisions on a meticulous evaluation of information and cues. An advantageous aspect of the theory lies in its ability to mitigate risks, as trust can function as a mechanism to reduce uncertainty and risk in various interactions. However, the theory has notable weaknesses, particularly in terms of vulnerability and subjectivity. The concept of trust involves vulnerability, making individuals susceptible to disappointment if trust is betrayed. Additionally, trust is subjective, as what inspires trust in one person may not necessarily have the same effect on another.

Methodology

This research employed an ex-post facto research design, utilizing historical data derived from economic events that have already occurred. The study focused on a population comprising twenty-two (22) quoted insurance companies in Nigeria consistently listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) Limited from 2012 to 2022. The sample for the study included the same twenty-two (22) insurance companies present on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31, 2022. The study employed the Census sampling methodology, recommended for studies with a relatively small number of units, as it encompasses all elements of the population, ensuring unbiased representation and robust generalization of findings. Data for the study were sourced from secondary sources, specifically the financial statements and notes to accounts of the selected Nigerian insurance companies. The regression analysis was carried out using the Random Effect method.

The model specification comprises two sets of variables: the dependent set, represented by the response variable proxied through return on assets (ROE), and the independent variables, also referred to as explanatory variables, represented by audit fees (AFEE), audit firm size (AFS), and

audit committee independence (ACI). The linear equation specified for the model, as utilized by Awinbugri and Gyimah (2019) and Iliemena *et al.* (2019), is outlined below:

$$ROE = f(AFEE + AFS + ACI).$$

Expressing the above equation in the econometric form, the equation becomes:

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AFEE_{it} + \beta_2 AFS_{it} + \beta_3 ACI_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots \text{Model.}$$

Where:

ROE = represents the return on equity that measures the dependent variable (firm performance);

β_0 = a constant;

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficients of the indicators of the audit quality;

AFEE = represents audit fee – an indicator of audit quality;

AFS = represents audit firm size - an indicator for audit quality;

ACI = represents audit committee independence - an indicator of audit quality;

i = represents firms/companies;

t = Periods; and

μ = Error term (Unused variables effect).

Variable Measurement and Justification

Table 1: Variable Measurement and Justification

Variable	Type	Measurement	Justification
Return on Equity (ROE)	Dependent	Profit after tax divided by the total equity capital.	Afifa and Saleh (2023); Idogho and Daniel (2020); Awinbugri and Gyimah (2019).
Audit Fee (AFEE)	Independent	Natural logarithm of audit fees paid per annum.	Hyarat <i>et al.</i> (2023); Orji and Nwaeze (2022); Syder <i>et al.</i> (2022); Afolabi and
Audit Firm Size (AFS)	Independent (Dichotomous)	If audited by the Big4 audit firms assign 1, otherwise, assign 0.	Afifa and Saleh (2023); Ozegbe and Jeroh (2022); Megeid 2022); Shubita (2021).
Audit Committee Independence (ACI)	Independent	The proportion of independent non-executive directors on the audit committee	Ozegbe and Jeroh (2022); Ehiedu and Toria (2022); Meah <i>et al.</i> (2021); Amahalu and Obi (2020).

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2023.

Results and Discussion

The analysis was conducted using the Descriptive statistics, correlation, normality test and heteroskedasticity test. The model estimation was by Randon effect regression method.

Descriptive Statistics

The data used for this were statistically summarized in the descriptive statistical table below which shows the number of observations, the mean, the standard deviation, the minimum and the maximum values of the variables.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
roe	264	0.0187	0.0937	-0.692	0.432
l_afee	260	4.2169	0.3215	3.32	5.19
afs	260	0.5462	0.4988	0	1
aci	264	0.4057	0.1052	0.2	0.6

Source: Stata software.

The statistics presented in Table 2 above indicate that the return on assets (ROE) for the 22 insurance companies in Nigeria, on average, is 0.0187 with a standard deviation of 0.0937. This suggests that the average ROE during the study period was approximately 0.02, a value lower than the standard deviation (0.10). This implies a wider dispersion of ROE, indicating fast growth rates among the companies. In contrast, the independent variables (AFEE, AFS, and ACI) exhibit mean values of 4.2169, 0.5462, and 0.4057, respectively, which surpass their standard deviations (0.3215, 0.4988, and 0.1052). This suggests that these variables had narrower dispersion and slower growth rates over the study period. Notably, the mean values of all variables fall between their minimum and maximum values, confirming a consistent and even distribution of the data.

Correlation Test for Multicollinearity

The coefficients of correlation among the variables, presented in Table 3, reveal the assessment of multicollinearity presence or absence in the model. The criterion for identifying multicollinearity is based on a decision rule: if the correlation between any two independent variables exceeds 0.85, multicollinearity is considered present. The consequence of multicollinearity is an elevation in the R-squared, also known as the coefficient of determination

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	ROE	L_AFEE	AFS	ACI
ROE	1.0000			
L_AFEE	-0.1681*	1.0000		
AFS	-0.0496	0.5887*	1.0000	
ACI	0.0403	0.1000	0.0985	1.0000
	0.0066	0.0000	0.1130	
	0.4256	0.1077		

Source: Stata software.

The outcomes presented in Table 3 indicate a significant negative correlation between AFEE and the dependent variable (ROE) at -0.1681, and AFS also exhibits a significant negative correlation at -0.0496. The correlation between AFEE is noteworthy, while ACI shows a positive but insignificant correlation at 0.0403. Among the independent variables under consideration, AFEE demonstrates a significant positive correlation with AFS at 0.5887%, but an insignificant correlation at 0.1000% with ACI. ACI has a positive but insignificant correlation with AFS at 0.0985. In summary, none of the independent variables exhibit a correlation exceeding 0.85, indicating that multicollinearity is not a concern in this model.

Skewness/Kurtosis Test for Normality

Table 4 presents the outcomes of the normality test conducted on data residuals using the Skewness/Kurtosis method to assess the distribution pattern of the residuals. According to the decision rule, a model is considered to have abnormally distributed residuals if its p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, whereas a p-value higher than 0.05 indicates normally distributed residuals.

Table 4: Skewness/Kurtosis Test

Variable	Obs	----- joint -----		adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
		Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)		
residuals	260	0.6801	0.2193	1.69	0.4291

Source: Stata software.

The results presented in Table 4 above reveal that the model possesses a p-value of 0.4291, surpassing the critical value of 0.05. According to the decision rule, this observation suggests that the residuals were distributed normally (symmetrically).

Heteroskedasticity Test

Table 5, provided below, showcases the results of a heteroskedasticity test conducted to assess the stability of the residual variance in the model. Following a decision rule, any model with a p-value exceeding 0.05 indicates residuals with a consistent variance, whereas a model with a p-value lower than or equal to 0.05 signifies residuals without a constant variance.

Table 5: Heteroskedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
Ho:	Constant variance
Variables:	fitted values of ROE
chi2(1)	125.74
Prob > chi2	0.0000

Source: Stata software.

The heteroskedasticity test results presented in Table 5 indicate a p-value of 0.0000, suggesting the presence of residuals with non-constant variance in the model. This violates a key assumption of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, which requires residuals to exhibit constant variance. Consequently, conducting estimation using the OLS regression method is not appropriate in this case.

Regression Analysis

The regression analysis of the model was conducted with the aid of the random effects estimation.

Table 8: Regression Analysis

ro	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z
L_AFEE	-0.0581	0.0297	-1.96	0.050
AFS	0.0213	0.0172	1.24	0.216
ACI	0.0035	0.0084	0.41	0.681
_cons	0.0165	0.0211	0.78	0.674
R-sqd overall				0.4173
Wald chi2(5)				26.61
Prob> chi2				0.0027

Source: Stata software.

The overall R-squared, as presented in Table 8 above, demonstrates a value of 0.4173. This suggests that the collective impact of the three independent variable indicators—namely AFEE,

AFS, and ACI—accounts for approximately 42% of the influence on the dependent variable (financial performance), which is measured by the return on equity (ROE) of the twenty-two quoted insurance companies in Nigeria spanning from 2011 to 2022. The positive Wald chi-square value of 26.61 and a $\text{prob} > \chi^2$ of 0.0027 (significantly at the 1% level) indicate that the model is well-fitted and the findings are robust.

Table 8 presented above, indicates that the audit fee (AFEE) has a noteworthy negative impact (-1.96) on the financial performance of Nigerian insurance companies, as represented by return on equity (ROE), with a coefficient value of -0.0581. These findings reject the null hypothesis one (H_{01}), asserting that audit fees do not significantly affect the financial performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. The findings suggest that holding all other variables constant, a one-unit increase in the audit fee's naira value results in an approximate 0.6-unit reduction in financial performance. This negative relationship between audit fee and financial performance could be due to the fact that firms that perform poorly might lack efficient financial systems, resulting in more work for auditors to verify accuracy and completeness. The higher the audit effort, the more costly the audit becomes, potentially reducing overall firm performance. This aligns with the conclusions drawn by Hyarat *et al.* (2023), Orji and Nwaeze (2022). This finding supports the agency theory which advocates for effective monitoring of management despite the effect the cost of monitoring would have on their returns.

The results in Table 8 also disclose that audit firm size (AFS) has an insignificant positive effect (1.24) on the financial performance of Nigerian insurance companies, as measured by return on equity (ROE), with a coefficient value of 0.0213. This implies the acceptance of the null hypothesis two (H_{02}). This implies that keeping all other variables constant, a one-unit increase in the engagement of Big 4 audit firms enhances financial performance by approximately 0.2 units. This finding aligns with Fassung and Valery (2022) and Megeid (2022). Tult his insignificant positive effect could be as a result of macroeconomic factors like exchange rate volatility, inflation, or weak consumer demand which may overshadow the benefits of having a large audit firm or an independent audit committee. For smaller firms, the costs associated with hiring a larger audit firm or ensuring a fully independent audit committee may not yield proportional benefits. These smaller firms may lack the complexity that would require extensive

auditing or oversight, making the relationship with performance insignificant. One way the smaller firms can overcome these challenges is Governments or industry bodies should offer subsidies or incentives to help small firms afford high-quality audit services. This finding is in support of the Theory of Trust and Value Creation as the positive relationship between audit firm size and financial performance is positive, indicating that the involvement of the big4 auditors inspire more confidence and hence more investment leading to higher returns on equity.

Furthermore, Table 8 illustrates that audit committee independence (ACI) has an insignificant positive effect (0.41) on the financial performance of Nigerian insurance companies, represented by return on equity (ROE), with a coefficient value of 0.0035. These results lead to the acceptance of the null hypothesis three (Ho₃). This implies that, without any other changes in variables, a one-unit increase in the number of independent non-executive directors on the audit committee enhances financial performance by approximately 0.004 units. This finding aligns with those of Megeid (2022), Meah *et al.* (2021) and supports the Agency theory which promotes the engagement of indirect directors who when appointed unto audit committees would discharge their monitoring responsibility without fear or favour since they are involve in the day-to day running of the firms.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The audit fee constitutes a critical factor impacting financial performance, stemming from the fact that it is drawn from profits. A higher audit fee, when charged and paid, leads to a reduction in net earnings and a diminished return on equity. The size of the audit firm may enhance performance to some extent, possibly because larger audit firms contribute to client firms' improvement but simultaneously claim a substantial portion of profits as fees, thereby minimizing their overall impact. Although audit committee independence is crucial for ensuring audit quality, its potential to enhance financial performance appears limited. The study offers the following recommendations:

- i) Insurance company management seeking improved financial performance should avoid engaging auditors charging exorbitant fees, as these higher fees significantly reduce profits.
- ii) Encouraging the engagement of large audit firms could exert a substantial influence on financial performance. This is particularly relevant since a majority of the studied firms were not

audited by the big four throughout the twelve-year study period, resulting in the current lack of significant impact.

iii) Enhancing audit committee independence, determined by the presence of independent non-executive directors on the committee, is recommended to transform its effect on financial performance from insignificant to significant

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